

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF MARRIED NON-COMMISSIONED FEMALE POLICE OFFICERS

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Lived Experiences of Married Non-Commissioned Female Police Officers

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Abstract

Using the qualitative approach, this research delved into the lived experiences of thirteen female police officers serving the Philippine National Police (PNP) to understand how they navigate and cope with the unique challenges inherent in their profession. Today, women constitute a significant part of the PNP, holding key organizational positions. Their success is attributed to their determination, hard work, and resilience, challenging traditional gender roles to make a meaningful impact in their communities. The findings underscore the myriad challenges faced by female police officers, particularly concerning work-family conflict, gender inequality, and navigating a male-dominated field. The data illuminates the influence of cultural context, deeply ingrained family values, and societal expectations, highlighting the significant impact on married female officers. The strong emphasis on traditional family roles within Filipino culture, coupled with the collectivist family structure, introduces distinct challenges, shaping the experiences of these officers as they strive to balance demanding law enforcement careers with familial responsibilities. Addressing these multifaceted challenges necessitates a comprehensive and culturally sensitive approach. Beyond the overarching goal of changing societal norms and attitudes, specific attention must be given to tailoring support systems to the unique cultural context of the Philippines. This includes the imperative implementation of policies that recognize and accommodate the distinctive challenges married female officers face, such as addressing work-family balance issues and managing societal expectations placed upon them and their families.

Keywords: *lived experiences and non-commissioned police officers*

Introduction

In the Philippines, the position of Filipino women has seen a significant transformation, contesting conventional notions that restricted them to domestic duties. In recent years, women have progressively entered several sectors, including law enforcement, challenging traditional conventions. Since achieving independence, Filipino women have actively engaged in public service, with the 20th century seeing a significant increase in their presence within the police force. Initially, several women, usually occupied with domestic responsibilities, see enlistment in the police force to serve their communities while supporting their families. Despite cultural expectations and skepticism about their fitness for police service, Filipino women persisted, demonstrating their competencies and often surpassing their male colleagues.

Currently, women comprise a substantial segment of the Philippine National Police (PNP), occupying important roles within the institution. Their success is ascribed to their perseverance, diligence, and persistence, defying conventional gender norms to effectuate a significant influence on their communities. Female police officers in the Philippines do many duties, including patrol duties, investigations, traffic management, and involvement in specialized operations like counter-narcotics and counter-terrorism initiatives. They participate in community policing, working with residents to tackle crime and safety issues.

In addition to their work in the police force, female officers are essential to many projects and programs aimed at bettering the lives of children and women. Engaging in civic activities and community outreach programs, working with groups that combat domestic abuse, and participating in educational programs for young females on personal safety and self-defense are all part of this. The Women and Children Protection Desks (WCPDs) have been set up at each police station in the Philippines as part of the Philippine National Police's efforts to encourage and empower female officers. These workstations show how caring and sensitive the organization is by helping children and women who have been victims of abuse. The Philippine National Police continues to prioritize expanding the participation of women in the force, with the goal of reaching 20% by 2022, notwithstanding the progress that has been accomplished. A work-family conflict that arises from the difficulties of reconciling family duties with one's employment is one of the many obstacles that female law enforcement personnel encounter.

By delving into the difficulties female police officers in the Philippines encounter while juggling their professional responsibilities with those of caregivers, spouses, and community members, this study hopes to fill a knowledge vacuum on their lived experiences. The study's overarching goal is to help shed light on the specific challenges faced by women in law enforcement and to provide solutions for creating a more welcoming environment for all employees by diving into their stories. Aiming to shed light on why many married female officers continually seek to preserve their marriages despite problems in both their professional and personal life, the researcher was motivated by the rising incidence of marital troubles among uniformed personnel. This study is in line with the efforts of the Philippine National Police General Hospital's Director of Health Service and Chief of the Department of Psychiatry, as it provides detailed information for the purpose of developing programs to aid the mental health of PNP officers who are struggling to balance their personal and professional lives. The researcher was motivated to boost the unit's performance and the Department's support programs by conducting this study while still a junior officer.

Research Questions

The study aimed to explore the lived experiences of non-commissioned female police officers. Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What challenges can be gleaned from the experiences of the participants?
2. Based on the findings, what recommendations can we propose?

Literature Review

Challenges of working in a male-dominated field

To begin, female police officers in the Philippines have a great deal of physical difficulty on the job. Police work often demands stamina and strength, which may be problematic for women since their physiological qualities are typically lower than men's. To overcome this obstacle, we must replace strength-based criteria with gender-neutral physical standards that evaluate skills relevant to the job. We can evaluate the two ladies based on their competence in critical areas if we establish fair and objective standards. Two, a hostile work environment is exacerbated by the perception and preconceptions surrounding women in law enforcement. We need a multi-pronged strategy to overcome these prejudices. The public may be better informed about the strengths and accomplishments of female police officers via public education initiatives and outreach programs that aim to dispel prejudices. Furthermore, by addressing biases and preconceptions in the workplace, diversity training may help law enforcement organizations create an environment where everyone is treated with dignity and fairness. Striking a balance between job and family life is the third obstacle that was addressed. Women police officers may already have a heavier burden at home and in the caregiving department due to their unexpected schedules and irregular work hours. This problem may be mitigated, and work-life balance can be promoted for all officers, regardless of gender, by instituting family-friendly and flexible working hours, paid parental leave, and childcare assistance. The last major issue is the lack of opportunities for female police officers to grow in their careers. To overcome these obstacles, we need to establish fair promotion procedures that focus on performance and merit rather than gender. It is critical to ensure that female police officers have the same opportunity as male officers to further their careers via training and development. To further assist and empower women who aspire to leadership roles, support groups and mentoring programs might be set up. To sum up, if we want to make the police force in the Philippines a better place for women, we need to do things like reduce the physical demands of the job, fight prejudice and stereotyping, encourage a healthy work-life balance, and eliminate obstacles to promotion. Law enforcement organizations may support gender equality and fully use the potential of their female officers by creating an inclusive and welcoming work environment. While these initiatives may not directly benefit individual officers, they do help build stronger, more effective police departments that can better meet the needs of their communities.

The emotional and mental strain of police work

There is widespread agreement that police officers, regardless of gender, endure substantial psychological and emotional stress on the job. Dealing with violent incidents, trauma, and high-stress circumstances is a part of being a police officer. Gender prejudices and preconceptions are present in both the police force and society at large, which may make things even more difficult for female officers. Defeating prejudices and preconceptions based on gender is a major obstacle for female commanders. Pressure to prove oneself and make a show is common for female officers in a traditionally male-dominated profession. They may experience increased tension and anxiety as a result of this need to prove themselves as competent professionals (Kuo & Wienclaw, 2017). Further adding to emotional and mental strain is misogyny from community members or coworkers. Finding a balance between job and home life is another major obstacle for female cops. Working long and unpredictable hours as a police officer may make it hard for women to take care of their families at home. According to Patterson et al. (2018), individuals may have negative effects on their health and relationships with their loved ones because of the accompanying emotions of shame, anxiety, and exhaustion. Female police officers already have enough mental and emotional challenges without having to deal with the added pressure of community expectations and views. In community police, female officers are stereotyped as being kinder and more sympathetic. Although this may bring them joy, it may also put extra emotional strain on them. Meanwhile, some people of the community may question their skills and criticize them since they aren't as strong as men (Kuo & Wienclaw, 2017). Finally, the mental and emotional health of female police officers might suffer due to the demands of the job. Conditions including post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, and anxiety may develop after being exposed to violent events, high-stress circumstances, or traumatic experiences in general (Violanti & Paton, 2015). Officers may become emotionally distant from the public because of their prolonged exposure to trauma and violent incidents. No matter their gender, police officers experience the same mental and emotional tolls on the job. Nevertheless, the intrinsic nature of police employment, societal expectations, gender-based prejudices and biases, and the difficulty of juggling work and family life may provide special problems for female officers. Organizations within the police force have an obligation to assist their members in dealing with these stresses and putting their mental and emotional health first. Our police force will be stronger and healthier if we fix these problems.

Impact of police work on family life

No matter the officer's gender, the stress and demands of police job may have a major influence on their personal lives (Patterson et al., 2018). Finding a balance between job and family life may be especially difficult for female police officers. Working long and

unexpected hours is a common problem for female police officers. If a police officer has small children or is a single parent, the stress and difficulty of coordinating family obligations with their irregular work schedule—which often includes night shifts and weekends—can put a strain on family connections. A further obstacle that female police officers could encounter is the mental and emotional strain that comes with doing police job. According to Patterson et al. (2018), police personnel often face stressful and distressing circumstances, which may result in anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Officers' inability to control their emotions at home, leading to irritability or estrangement from loved ones, might have a negative effect on family life. Furthermore, female police officers may face harassment and discrimination because of their gender, which may have an effect on their emotional health, productivity at work, and quality of life at home (Kuo & Wienclaw, 2017). Uneven compensation, overlooked for promotions, and exclusion from informal networks are only a few examples of the many manifestations of gender-based discrimination. In the workplace, harassment may take many forms, including unwelcome approaches, statements, or actions that foster an unsafe atmosphere. Officers' relationships with their families may be affected by the stress, worry, and emotional weariness brought on by these situations. Additionally, female police officers can need some assistance juggling the expectations of their community with those of their job. Community policing includes visiting events, giving speeches to community organizations, and collaborating with youth programs; many police agencies urge officers to participate in these activities. While these pursuits often pay off in the end, they may eat up a lot of time and put more pressure on an already hectic work schedule. To sum up, the complicated subject of how police employment affects the family lives of female officers is one that families and departments alike need to pay attention to and help one another with. When people are emotionally and mentally drained from trying to meet the demands of their jobs, families, and communities, it may have a negative effect on their relationships and health. Helping police officers balance their personal and professional lives is an important part of doing a good job, and we can all do our part by offering resources like flexible work schedules, counseling services, and workplace policies that promote gender equality.

Gender inequality in the Workplace

Women in law enforcement, like women in all other fields, face the persistent problem of gender disparity. When it comes to juggling job, family, and community duties, female police officers have distinct obstacles that men officers may not have to deal with (Chan, 2018; Martin & Jurik, 2017; Wilson & Dalton, 2018). Discrimination and bigotry are major obstacles for female police officers. Gender equality has come a long way, but women still don't make up nearly enough of the police force. Discrimination based on gender may manifest in a variety of ways, including but not limited to fewer mentorship and training opportunities, improper conduct and harassment, and even job or promotion rejection (Chan, 2018; Wilson & Dalton, 2018). The need for female police officers to be physically healthy and strong is another obstacle they encounter. For a long time, police agencies' fitness standards were skewed toward male officers, making it harder for women to fulfill them. As a result, women may face obstacles to promotion and may not be considered for specialized units that need more physical fitness (Martin & Jurik, 2017; Women in Federal Law Enforcement, 2021). It may be difficult for female police officers to juggle their professional and personal lives. Maintaining a work-life balance may be tough for police officers due to the nature of their profession, which often requires long and unpredictable hours, including evenings and weekends. According to research by Chan (2018) and Women in Federal Law Enforcement (2021), female police may encounter prejudice or discrimination if they seek time off to attend to family responsibilities, such as taking care of children or elderly relatives.

These are just some of the obstacles that female police officers may encounter on the job. Some people of the community may not value female police officers or think they aren't as good as male policemen. The result could be complicated relationships or even hazardous work conditions (Martin & Jurik, 2017; Wilson & Dalton, 2018). Law enforcement agencies and other groups may help female officers overcome these obstacles by fostering a more welcoming and equal work environment. This involves making sure that all officers, regardless of gender, are physically fit, offering equal training and mentorship opportunities, and aggressively recruiting and promoting women. According to Women in Federal Law Enforcement (2021) and Chan (2018), departments may also institute rules that promote work-life balance by providing employees with flexible scheduling alternatives. More than just initiatives in the workplace, larger social shifts are required to reduce gender disparity and empower women who work for the police. Some examples of this kind of activism include fighting for wage equality and other forms of gender inequality, promoting work-family balance regulations, and combating prejudices and stereotypes based on gender (Martin & Jurik, 2017). A multipronged strategy is needed to address the complicated problem of gender disparity in the workplace. We can assist guarantee that all police officers, regardless of gender, have a fair shot at success by fighting for a more welcoming and equal work environment for female cops.

Trauma and stress from handling violent crimes

When coping with the stress and trauma of violent crimes, female police officers in the Philippines encounter distinct obstacles. Domestic abuse, sexual assault, and other types of violence against women are often responded to by female cops in this nation, which has a high crime rate. For female police officers, not having the backing of their peers and bosses is just one more obstacle they must overcome. Researchers Lontoc and Umil (2020) found that female Filipino police officers had more reports of gender-based violence and discrimination than their male colleagues. Female police officers may find it more challenging to deal with the stress and trauma of their jobs if they experience feelings of isolation because of this. A further obstacle is the inadequate funding for mental health services. According to research by Duka and Maralit (2020), the stigmatization of mental health concerns prevents many Filipino police officers, particularly female officers, from seeking treatment when they need it. Officers' emotional and physical well-being might be negatively impacted if they do not get treatment for trauma and stress. In addition, there may be issues with family support and work-

life balance for female police officers in the Philippines. Many Filipino female police officers have a hard time juggling their job and home lives, especially taking care of children and the elderly, according to research by Vargas and De Guzman (2019). Coping with the trauma and stress of the job may be challenging for female police, and this can contribute to their stress and burnout. Female police officers in the Philippines need more resources and assistance from their agencies if they are to overcome these obstacles. Some examples of this kind of assistance include trauma-informed care training, peer support, and therapy. The physical health of female police officers is greatly affected by institutionalized discrimination and gender-based violence, which must be addressed by police agencies. Finally, when it comes to coping with the stress and trauma associated with addressing violent crimes, female police officers in the Philippines have distinct obstacles. Problems with work-life balance, family support, mental health resources, and prejudice are all part of this list. There must be more support and tools for female police officers so they can deal with the stress and trauma they face on the job. If these obstacles are removed, female police officers will be able to serve their communities and increase public safety without sacrificing their emotional or physical health.

Methodology

Research Design

The research questions and goals are well-aligned with the phenomenological technique, which was chosen for this study with care (Creswell, 2013). Phenomenology is a way of doing qualitative research that allows you to zero in on people's actual experiences inside a particular setting. Key Reasons for Choosing Phenomenology:

Exploring Lived Experiences: The primary objective is to delve into the lived experiences of female police officers in the Philippines. Phenomenology excels in uncovering the essence of these experiences, providing nuanced insights into the challenges, coping mechanisms, and perspectives these women encounter in their roles.

Subjectivity and Individual Perspectives: Recognizing the importance of subjectivity, phenomenology enables an in-depth exploration of the diverse experiences of female police officers. This approach avoids oversimplification, acknowledging the unique encounters and responses everyone brings to the challenges they face.

Holistic Understanding: Phenomenology allows for a holistic understanding of participants' worlds, identifying patterns, commonalities, and variations in how female police officers perceive and navigate challenges in their professional and personal lives.

Contextual Relevance: Tailored to the context-specific nature of the research, phenomenology delves into the cultural, social, and organizational dynamics influencing the experiences of female police officers in the Philippines.

Policies and Interventions: Phenomenological findings offer valuable insights for developing targeted policies and interventions, aiding in the enhancement of well-being and professional growth for female officers.

Open-Ended Inquiry: Phenomenology supports open-ended inquiry, allowing participants to express themselves freely. This aligns with the research's goal of providing a platform for authentic storytelling, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of female police officers.

This research study employs a qualitative design, specifically utilizing in-depth interviews to explore the lived experiences of female police officers (Creswell, 2013). This method, well-suited for interpreting the meanings and experiences of individuals, facilitates a rich and detailed exploration of the subjective and personal experiences of female police officers. Its key components are recruitment, data collection, and data analysis involving thematic analysis. This research methodology is tailored to offer a profound understanding of the lived experiences of female police officers, unraveling the complexities of their professional and personal challenges.

Participants

Married female police officers were the primary subjects of the research, which recruited individuals with suitable work experience. The researcher specified eligibility requirements and sent out letters to various police units to recruit subjects. After receiving a list of possible volunteers via a messaging app, the researcher proceeded to screen them further by considering their employment experience and family ties. Thirteen people were chosen for the research because they fulfilled the requirements. The researcher communicated the study's goal using SMS texts, and participants were interviewed at their convenience. Participants were also apprised of how the research may be advantageous to the institution and their female counterparts in the force.

Instrument

The research instrument employed in this study consisted of the following sections:

Informed consent. Informed consent providing the participants of the study with information about the study, including its purpose, procedures, potential risks and benefits, and their rights as participants, and obtaining their agreement to participate voluntarily. Informed consent is an essential ethical principle in research, as it ensures that participants are fully informed about the study and can decide whether to participate or not. The researcher was responsible for obtaining this consent through their signatures and respecting their right to withdraw their participation at any time after the study has begun.

Information sheet. An information sheet is a document that provides information about a specific topic or study. In the context of a research study, an information sheet is typically provided to potential participants as part of the informed consent process. It is designed to inform participants about the study's purpose, procedures, the methods being used to collect data (such as in-depth interviews), the anticipated duration of the study, and the potential risks and benefits of participation. In this research on the lived experiences of female police officers, the information sheet also required the participants to provide some demographic information about themselves with the assurance of confidentiality.

Aide Memoir. This section of the instrument was used to gather information from the co-researchers. The researcher believed that a semi-structured interview based on the study's aim would be able to extract the necessary information needed to understand the co-researchers' experiences. The semi-structured interview aided in producing reliable and meaningful outcomes.

The following tools or devices were used by the researcher in the conduct of the interview.

Recorder. A recorder is a device used to record audio or visual information. In a research study, a recorder records interviews or focus groups with participants to capture and preserve the data collected during the study. In this study, digital audio recorders were used by the researcher with the consent of the participants. Digital audio recorders are specifically designed to record audio. They typically have built-in microphones and can store audio files digitally. Digital audio recorders can help record interviews or focus groups, as they are portable and easy to use. Many smartphones have built-in audio recording capabilities, making them another option for recording audio data in research studies. It is essential to ensure that participants are informed and consenting to the recording of the research sessions. It is also essential to ensure that the recorder is functioning correctly, and that the quality of the recording is sufficient for the study.

Field-Notes. Field notes are detailed information and systematic observations recorded by a researcher while conducting a study in the field. Field notes are typically handwritten and can include a wide range of information, including descriptions of events, conversations, observations, and participant interactions. Field notes are an essential tool for researchers, as they provide a record of the research process and can be used to supplement other data sources, such as interviews or surveys. Field notes can be handy in qualitative research studies, as they allow researchers to capture detailed and nuanced information about the experiences and perspectives of participants. In this study, the field notes included observations about the working environment and culture of the police department, descriptions of interactions with participants, and any other relevant comments or insights that the researcher gathered while conducting the study. Field notes were written after an observation or interaction as soon as possible to ensure the data was fresh in the researcher's memory. The researcher was also careful to record his observations objectively and not allow his own biases or preconceptions to influence his writings.

Procedure

The following steps were followed by the researcher in the study: To get the approval of the Investigation Unit Chief, the researcher explained the study's purpose, the criteria for selecting target participants, the informed consent, and the study's confidentiality. Then, the request for potential participants for the study was made. Then, the researcher formally asked for the approval of the target co-researchers. Co-researchers were informed about the purpose of the research and asked for their willingness to participate. Their interest and personal decision to become respondents were taken into consideration. He presented and duly explained the informed consent content and stated that the co-researcher could withdraw anytime. Before the interview session, the researcher provided the co-researchers with an information sheet to fill up. The researcher clarified that their identities would be kept confidential. The research data gathering was pushed through once the co-researchers stated they would participate in the study and signed the informed consent. Also, the researcher asked for their approval to record the interview. The interview focused on the experiences of the married Female Police Officer. After each interview, the researcher notified the co-researcher concerning the next meeting so that a proper closing would be held. Finally, the researcher asked for consent from the co-researchers to include all the information or only excerpts in the documentation. Very personal data and other sensitive collections were kept with strict confidentiality. After the interview, the researcher debriefed the co-researchers and asked probing questions to merge the findings. That helped the researcher in developing an immediate reflection of the conclusions. In the debriefing, the participants were fully informed about the study and could ask questions for clarification. Data gathered were consulted with the co-researchers to check for validation and confirmation of their experiences and responses to the interview.

Through notetaking, audio recordings, and observation of non-verbal cues during the interview, necessary data were documented and collated to be analyzed the data analysis phase. Data analysis systematically reviews and interprets the data collected during a research study. The specific data analysis procedures used in a study depend on the research questions being addressed, the research design, and the data collected. In a research study on the lived experiences of female police officers, the data analysis procedure involved several steps, including:

Data Analysis

Reading and Re-reading. The researcher came up with rich evidence from the co-researcher's narratives; reading and re-reading were done as much as possible. With the advantage of reading and re-reading, the researcher analyzed and reviewed the co-researcher's data. Furthermore, the researcher understood the main ideas after re-reading them.

Initial Noting. The researcher took note of the crucial points in the gathered data. In this stage, the researcher could come up with comments, and other statements were also noted.

Developing Emergent Themes. From the narratives, the researcher investigated possible emerging themes. The researcher provided a short description of the themes developed from the notes. The short explanation was advantageous for the readers to understand how the researcher constructed the themes.

Searching for Connections Across Themes. The researcher's identified themes were clustered. Related themes were merged to avoid redundancy, and themes with the same patterns were included in a separate column.

Moving to the Next Case. The researcher repeated the procedure for the following co-researcher's narrative. It aided the researcher in understanding each of the co-researchers' narratives comprehensively

Looking for Patterns Across Cases. The researcher then combined each emerging theme from the co-researcher's narratives. The summary of significant themes, subthemes, and critical responses was made in table format. That helped the researcher organize the major themes and subthemes and further formalize the findings.

Member Checking. Member checking is an opportunity for members (co-researchers) to check (verify) aspects of the interpretation of the data they provided (J. A. Carlson, 2010). Data gathered were returned to participants to check for validation and confirmation of their experiences and responses to the interview. That helped the researcher determine whether the data analysis was congruent with the participants' experiences and encouraged trustworthiness in the study.

Ethical Considerations

In the conduct of the study, the researcher considered the following ethical factors: The vulnerability of the participants. In choosing the participants, the researcher assumed that the co-researchers could decide whether to participate in the study provided. The researcher explained the scope of the study. Caution was prioritized in obtaining informed consent for the entire duration of the research. Risks, benefits, and safety: A careful assessment of predictable risk and burden guided the study. The researcher took precautions to avoid the study's negative impact on the well-being of the policewomen who participated. After the interview, through debriefing, the participants were fully informed about the study and were allowed to ask questions for clarification. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information: The researcher observed the value of transparency. The researcher did not identify the participants' information that may expose them to probable harm and social dishonor. Additionally, the researcher emphasized the participant's right to withdraw his data or information and refuse to answer any question. The participant's right to privacy has been respected.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results, their analysis, and their interpretation. Data from all questions and across participants were included to describe the participants in this study and establish the study's themes. The following themes and subthemes were extracted from the narratives of the female police officers who took part in this study:

On Family Role

Challenges as a mother and a Wife: Impact of police work on family life

On Work Role

Challenges at Work: Gender inequality in the workplace, Challenges of working in a male-dominated field, Psychological and Behavioral Strains, The emotional and mental strain of police work, and Trauma and stress from handling violent crimes

On Work-life Balance Issues

Time Strain: Balancing work and family responsibilities

The results are presented in tabulated form, followed by a discussion of the analysis and interpretation.

Table 1. Emergent Themes about Family Role: Challenges as Mother and Wife

Superordinate Theme	Sub-theme (Challenges)	Key Responses	Code
1. Family Role	1.1 Impact of police work on family life	“parehas silang nag deteriorate at na wala ang scholarship dahil dina daw nila ako nakikita sa bahay” (“They both deteriorated and lost their grant because they didn't see me at home anymore.”)	Ma’am Bravo
		“madami na kaming utang sa anak namin kasi palagi kaming wala sa mga activities lalu na at kailangan kami dun” (“We have a lot of debt for our child because our presence is needed in the activities that he needs us for, but we weren't there.”)	Ma’am Nancy
		“alam mo yung nag tratabaho ka tapos pag uwi mo mag tatalo pa kayo	Ma’am Alpha

minsang ng asawa mo dahil overtime ka" ("Do you know that feeling when you work and then when you come home, you sometimes argue with your spouse because you had to work overtime?")	
"yung asawa ko minsan na huli ko may kausap ng iba, sobrang galet ko nun, kasi daw palagi ako wala. Tama ba yun?" ("One time, I caught my spouse talking to someone else, and I got really angry because he said that I'm always unavailable. Is that right?")	Ma'am Charlie
"naalala ko nuon naabutan ko anak ko na nag try mag yosi, na iyak na lang ako kasi na papabayaang ko na mga anak ko dahil sa trabaho" ("I remember before when I caught my child trying to smoke, I just cried because I felt like I was neglecting my children because of work.")	Ma'am Echo
"minsang nga may panahon na nag talo kami ng asawa ko kasi pumasok ako sa office ng sabado. Pakiramdam nya daw wala na ako time sa kanila ng mga anak namin" ("There are times when my spouse and I would argue because I went to the office on a Saturday. They felt like I no longer had time for them and our children.")	Ma'am Delta
"Alam mo pinaka masakit sa trabaho natin? Mag trabaho ng sobra pero na papabayaang natin mga pamilya natin" ("You know what's most painful about our job? Working too much and neglecting our families.")	Ma'am Juliet
"lagi ako na punta ng office pag weekend para lang matapos yung compliance at ayun din ang dahilan kung bakit kami nag tatalo palagi mag asawa" ("I always go to the office on weekends just to finish the compliance, and that's also the reason why my spouse and I always argue.")	Ma'am Foxtrot

Theme 1: Family Role: Challenges as Mother and Wife

The impact of work on family is operationally defined as the measurable and observable effects of the demanding job duties and long working hours experienced by female police officers in the Philippines on their family relationships, emotional well-being, and the overall development of their children.

1.1 Sub-theme: Impact of police work on family life

These statements from female police officers in the Philippines highlight women's challenges when balancing work and family responsibilities. Their demanding job duties and long hours affect their family relationships and cause emotional distress, as can be gleaned from the following remark:

Ma'am Nancy: "*Madami na kaming utang sa anak namin kasi palagi kaming wala sa mga activities lalo na at kailangan kami dun*". ("We owe our child a lot because we couldn't be in activities where our presence is required.")

A study by Greenhaus and Powell (2006) found that work-family conflict, which occurs when work demands interfere with family responsibilities, significantly predicts employee stress and burnout. This stress does not only affect the person itself; it can also negatively affect their surroundings, their relationship with their partners, and their relationship with their child.

Ma'am Foxtrot: "*Lagi ako napunta ng office pag weekend para lang matapos yung compliance at ayun din ang dahilan kung bakit kami nag tatalo palagi mag asawa*." ("I always go to the office on weekends just to finish the compliance, and that's also the reason why my spouse and I always argue.")

The statement above shows how their work affects their relationship with their spouses. Weekends should be the time allotted for the family. A police officer is an officer twenty-four hours a day. They can be called for work anytime (Milton, 1972). Consequently, this is why they will have less time with their spouse, child, or family.

Another statement shows that one of the officers blames herself for her child's unhealthy habits.

Ma'am Echo: "*Naalala ko nuon naabutan ko anak ko na nag try mag yosi, na iyak na lang ako kasi napapabayaang ko na mga anak ko dahil sa trabaho*." ("I remember before when I caught my child trying to smoke, I just cried because I felt like I was neglecting my children because of work.")

Having limited time spent with a child while growing can affect their child's growth and development. Parental care is considered one of the most critical factors that help develop children's cognitive and non-cognitive abilities, especially in early childhood (Mao, M., Zang, L., & Zhang, H. 2020).

Several studies from 2006 and 2013 have also shown that less time spent with children negatively affects children's development in terms of their health status, daily behaviors, and in-school performance.

Table 2. *Emergent Themes about Work Role: Challenges at Work*

Superordinate Theme	Sub-themes (Challenges)	Key Responses	Code
2. Work Role	2.1 Gender Inequality in the Workplace	“isa lang na patunayan ko na mas matalino ang babaeng pulis. Ang mga lalake malalakas lang” ("I've proven that female police officers are smarter. Men are just physically stronger.")	Ma'am Lima
		“sinabi ko sa kanila na mas mas matured at matalino kaming mga babae” ("I told them to remember that women are more mature and intelligent than them.")	Ma'am Bravo
		“ramdam ko pag computer task ako agad kasi babae ako” " I am immediately tasked with computer- related tasks because I am a woman."	Ma'am Juliet
		“ayaw nila ako isama minsan sa operation kasi babae daw ako mabagal tumakbo” "They don't want to include me in operations sometimes because they say I am a woman and run slowly."	Ma'am Golf
		“lagi ako office work kahit meron naman akong traning pang intel” "I always do office work even though I have training for intelligence work."	Ma'am Delta
		“minsan pinag kukumpara nila ang cooking skills ko at trabaho bilang operatiba. Mas ok pa daw ako mag luto kesa mag aresto.” "Sometimes, they compare my cooking skills with my job as an operative. They say that I am better at cooking than arresting."	Ma'am Nancy
		“madalas office work ako kasi di ko daw kaya mag puyatan sa operatiba” "I often do office work because they say I can't handle staying late for operative work."	Ma'am Hotel
		2.2 Challenges of working in a male-dominated field	“Kailangan kong mag-adjust sa pagtatrabaho kasama ang mga lalaking may iba't ibang pananaw at pagpapahalaga, lalo na't nagmumula sila sa iba't ibang tribo.” ("I had to adjust to working with all men with different attitudes and values, especially coming from various tribes.")
	“SWAT po ako at lagi ko po sinu-subukang making sabayan parin sa kanila.” ("I'm in SWAT, and I'm trying to keep up with them.")		Ma'am Lima
	“Talagang may problema kapag ang mga lalaki at babae ay nagtatrabaho ng magkasama dahil minsan ay inii-assign nila ang mga gawain na hindi ko kaya harapin.” ("There's a problem when men and women work together because sometimes they assign tasks that I can't handle.")		Ma'am Alpha
	“minsan may mga joke po sila na green pero dapat marunong ka lang maki sakay” ("Sometimes they make green jokes, but you just have to know how to take them.")		Ma'am Nancy
	“ako po di ako mahilig uminom ng alak, pero ayun ang bonding ng mga kasamahan ko. No choice ako minsan nasama ako” ("I'm not fond of drinking alcohol, but that's how my colleagues bond. Sometimes I have no choice but to join them.")		Ma'am Golf
	“na iisip ko kung productive pa ba akong investigador” ("I wonder if I'm still productive as an investigator.")		Ma'am Golf
	“minsan kahit maliliit na bagay umiinit ang ulo ko” ("Sometimes, even the smallest things make me angry and frustrated.")		Ma'am Delta
	“Minsan tatawag sa school tapos na aksidente anak ko, ang hirap na lilito ka minsan sa ginagawa mo sa office.” ("Sometimes the school will call and tell me that my child had an accident; it's difficult because sometimes you're torn between what you're doing in the office.")		Ma'am Alpha
	2.3 Emotional and mental strain of police work	“Kahit gaano ka hirap, at dilikado dapat binabalanse parin natin ang lahat. Kasi sa PNP puro temtasyon eh” ("No matter how difficult it is, it's crucial to balance everything and not give in to temptation because there are many in the PNP.")	Ma'aam Juliet
“Mahirap mag paliwanag bakit lagi ako naka duty tapos lagi pa nag tatanong ang mga bata” ("It's hard to explain that we're always on duty, and the children always		Ma'am Hotel	

2.4 Trauma and Stress from handling violent crimes	ask.") "Di ko na sila na kakausap at nakikita o nakikitang nag aaral" ("I couldn't talk to them or see them studying.")	Ma'am India
	"Na subukan ko mag 24 hours na walang tulog, na apektuhan talaga yung kaso na hawak ko" ("I experienced 24 hours of no sleep, and it affected me in this case.")	Ma'am Mickey
	"Sobrang na stress talaga ako sa VAWC syempre nanay din ako" ("I'm stressed about the VAWC because I'm a mother.")	Ma'am Nancy
	"Ang kaso na iniharap sa akin ay tungkol sa isang babae na sinubukang patayin ng kanyang asawa. Binasag ang kanyang bungo at kinuha ang kanyang mata, kaya't kinuha ko ang kanyang pahayag sa ospital." ("The case brought to me was about a woman beaten to death by her husband. Her skull was shattered, and her eye was gouged out, so I took her statement to the hospital.")	Ma'am Lima
	"Meron kaming hinabol na criminal nuon sa Quiapo, sinu bukan niyang barilin kami ilang beses pero naka iwas kami" ("We were chasing a criminal before in Quiapo, he tried to shoot us several times, but we were able to dodge it.")	Ma'am Alpha
	"Alala ko noon sa SWAT ang saya pa namin naka Duty biglang may nag putukan sa Gilid namin pag kita ko kasamahan namin may tama nan ang bala sa balikat. Iba talaga na ramdaman ko nun" ("I remember back when I was in SWAT, we were on duty, and suddenly there was shooting near us. When I looked, one of our colleagues was hit in the shoulder. I felt different at that moment.")	Ma'am Delta
	"Intel ako nun sa bandang Bicutan, target namin drug addict. Namatay kasamahan namin pero na aresto naman suspect. Ilanga raw din ako di na ka tulog nun" ("I was an intelligence officer before in Bicutan; our target was drug addicts. One of our colleagues died, but we were able to arrest the suspect. I was awake for several nights after that incident.")	Ma'am Charlie
	"Bus Martial ako sa Edsa dati, sako na holdap yung sinasakyan ko. Wala ako magawa kundi lumaban kahit mag isa lang ako. Inisip ko talaga pag namatay ako sa oras nay un kawawa pamilya ko" ("I was a bus marshal on Edsa before, and my vehicle was being robbed. I couldn't do anything but fight, even though I was alone. I thought I died at that time; my family would be left helpless.")	Ma'am Golf
	"Meron sa barangay namin kahit naka off duty ako noon, may adik na lalake nan ang hostage sugatan na yung bata. Rumesponde ako kahit nakakatakot" ("There was an incident in our barangay where, even though I was off duty, a drug-addicted man had taken a child hostage and injured him. I responded even though it was scary.")	Ma'am Hotel
	"May suicidal case ako na hawak nun sa investigation, grabe kawaw yung bata tatay at mga kapatid niya ang gumagalaw sa kanya, wala kasi nanay niya nasa abroad, nakaka kulo talaga ng dugo" ("I had a suicidal case that I handled during the investigation; the situation was so sad. The child's father and siblings were the ones causing harm to the child since the mother was abroad. It made my blood boil.")	Ma'am Juliet
"Muntik na ako maaksidente sa motor kasi biglang nag karoon ako ng parang flashback ba tawag dun. Kasi naka kita ako ng sugatan sa bangketa" ("I almost had an accident on my motorcycle because I suddenly had what you call a 'flashback.' It's because I saw someone injured on the sidewalk.")	Ma'am Echo	

Theme 2: Challenges at Work: Work Role

2.1 Sub-Theme: Gender Inequality in the Workplace

Gender inequality in the workplace: The text highlights the issue of gender inequality in the workplace. The officer talks about how female police officers are more intelligent and mature than their male colleagues but how men are still perceived as physically more robust.

"Isa lang napatunayan ko, na mas matalino ang babaeng pulis. Ang mga lalake malalakas lang" ("I've proven that female police officers are smarter. Men are just physically stronger.")

Additionally, the National Institute of Justice (2020) has published a report on recruitment and retention strategies for women in law enforcement, acknowledging the unique challenges faced by female officers in a male-dominated field. These sources provide further

evidence to support the notion that female police officers may face systemic barriers and biases in their profession (Stromwall & Gertz, 2018; National Institute of Justice, 2020). Another officer also talks about how tasks are sometimes assigned based on gender and how men are given tasks that women can't handle.

Ma'am Hotel: "*Ayaw nila ako isama minsan sa operation kasi babae daw ako mabagal tumakbo.*" ("They don't want to include me in operations sometimes because they say I am a woman and I run slowly.")

The challenges and perceptions highlighted in these statements align with research on the experiences of female police officers. Stromwall and Gertz (2018) reviewed literature from 2009 to 2017, which found that female officers often face gender-based discrimination, stereotyping, and barriers to career advancement.

2.2 Sub Theme: Challenges of working in a male-dominated field

The challenges and perceptions highlighted in these statements align with research on the experiences of female police officers. Female police officers often face challenges working with male colleagues with different attitudes, values, and cultural backgrounds. They may also need to prove themselves and keep up with their male counterparts, particularly in elite units like SWAT. Assignments and tasks may be unfairly distributed, and female officers may feel marginalized or excluded from specific roles.

"*SWAT po ako at lagi ko po sinu-subukang makipagsabayan parin sa kanila.*"

("I'm in SWAT, and I'm trying to keep up with them.")

Moreover, female officers may encounter gender-based discrimination or harassment in the workplace, including inappropriate comments or jokes, which can create a hostile work environment.

Ma'am Nancy: "*Minsan may mga joke po sila na green pero dapat marunong ka lang maki sakay.*" ("Sometimes they make green jokes, but you just have to know how to take them.")

They may also struggle with balancing work and personal life, especially if the social activities of their colleagues involve behaviors that they are uncomfortable with or do not participate in, like drinking alcoholic beverages, as one of the participants mentioned. This can lead to isolation and exclusion from the team and affect the ability to form effective working relationships (Martin, 2017).

The police force is traditionally a male-dominated field, and female police officers often face unique challenges in their careers. One significant challenge is navigating and overcoming gender-based discrimination and bias in the workplace. Studies have shown that female officers may experience harassment, lack of support, and unfair treatment from their male colleagues (Lipsky & Smith, 2010; Schuck & Rosenbaum, 2017). These experiences can create a hostile work environment, affect job satisfaction, and hinder career advancement opportunities (Crank & Calderón, 2010).

Another challenge faced by female police officers is the need to prove themselves and earn respect from their male colleagues. Female officers are often under greater scrutiny and may be judged more harshly than their male counterparts, especially in physically demanding tasks or elite units like SWAT (Menzel & Franklin, 2016). This pressure to perform can create significant stress and burnout among female officers (Miller et al., 2014).

Sub-theme: Emotional and mental strain of police work

The text highlights the emotional and mental strain that police work can have on an individual. The narrative below shows that the officer talks about how she is stressed out and doesn't know how to handle her emotions, takes out her frustration on her husband, and sometimes feels angry and frustrated even over small things.

Ma'am Delta: "*minsan kahit maliliit na bagay umiinit ang ulo ko.*" ("Sometimes, even the smallest things make me angry and frustrated.")

Other challenges and perceptions highlighted in these statements align with research on the experiences of female police officers are: (1) Self-doubt about her ability to perform her job which shows in the statement: "*naiisip ko kung productive pa ba akong investigador*" (I question myself whether I am still productive as an investigator); (2) managing emotions and frustration which is shown in the statement given above, (3) difficulties of balancing work and family responsibilities, shown in the statement: "*Minsan tatawag sa school tapos na aksidente anak ko, ang hirap na lilito ka minsan sa ginagawa mo sa office*" (One time I got a call from the school because my child met an accident, I could no longer focus on what I was doing.); (4) resisting temptations, as seen in the statement "*Kahit gaano kahirap at delikado dapat binabalanse parin natin ang lahat. Kasi sa PNP puro temtasyon eh*" (No matter how difficult or dangerous, we need to balance everything, because there are many temptations around.); (5) maintaining family connection/relationship whilst working long hours, is shown in the statement "*Di ko na sila nakakausap at nakikita o nakikitang nag-aaral*" (I am no longer able to talk to them nor do I see them studying); (6) impact of stress and sleep deprivation on job performance, as shown in the statement "*Nasubukan ko mag 24 hours na walang tulog, naapektuhan talaga yung kaso na hawak ko*" (I have experienced losing sleep for 24 hours, and saw how it has affected my work) and lastly; (7) stress due to empathy towards same gender when dealing with cases of violence against women and children, which reflects on the statement "*Sobrang nastress talaga ako sa VAWC syempre nanay din ako*" (The VAWC cases truly stressed me, because I am a mother, too).

In this study, Fitzgerald and McNamara interviewed female police officers in Ireland to examine their experiences of policing work. The authors found that female officers faced challenges balancing work and family responsibilities and often struggled to be recognized as productive and effective. The study also highlighted the emotional toll of police work on female officers and the need for more significant support for officers experiencing stress and trauma. These findings align with the statements made by the female officer in the original discussion and support the assertion that the challenges and perceptions highlighted in the statements are consistent with the experiences of female police officers as documented in research.

Sub-Theme: Trauma and stress from handling violent crimes

The text highlights the trauma and stress that police officers experience when handling violent crimes. The officer talks about how she was affected by a case where a woman was beaten to death by her husband, and her 2-month-old child was put in a box and dropped out the window.

Ma'am Lima: *"Ang kaso na iniharap sa akin ay tungkol sa isang babae na sinubukang patayin ng kanyang asawa. Binasag ang kanyang bungo at kinuha ang kanyang mata, kaya't kinuha ko ang kanyang pahayag sa ospital."* ("The case brought to me was about a woman beaten to death by her husband. Her skull was shattered, and her eye was gouged out, so I took her statement to the hospital.")

According to the officer, she also cried and shivered during the case. It affected her emotionally to the point that remembering the case brings her back to tears, causing her stress and causing her to feel the same emotion as when she was first handed that case.

Several female police officers have shared their accounts of traumatic incidents they have experienced while on duty, including responding to domestic violence, shootings, robberies, and cases involving drug addicts and suicidal individuals. These experiences can have a significant impact on the mental health and well-being of police officers, potentially leading to symptoms of trauma, anxiety, and stress.

"Bus Martial ako sa Edsa dati, sakto na holdap yung sinasakyan ko. Wala ako magawa kundi lumaban kahit mag isa lang ako. Inisip ko talaga pag namatay ako sa oras na yun kawawa pamilya ko" ("I was a bus marshal at Edsa before, and my vehicle was being robbed. I couldn't do anything but fight, even though I was alone. I thought that if I died at that time, my family would be left helpless.")

However, it is essential to recognize the courage, resilience, and sense of duty exhibited by these officers in the face of these challenging and traumatic experiences. Despite the potential for burnout and emotional exhaustion, they continue to serve their communities with dedication and professionalism.

Table 3. Emergent Themes about Work-life Balance Issues

Superordinate Theme	Sub-theme	Key Responses	Code
3. Time Strain	3.1 Balancing work and family responsibilities	"mahirap maging nanay at maging Pulis sa totoo lang kasi kailangan mo minsan mamili eh Trabaho at Pamilya" ("It's hard being a mother and a police officer because you have to choose between your work and your children.")	Ma'am Juliet
		"Noong nagging patroller ako di kuna masyadong na priotize ang asawa ko at mga anak. Nasa barracks na lang ako kasi mas madali yun pag deployment" ("When I became a patroller, I no longer prioritized my married life because I was always deployed, alert, and staying in barracks, which caused some misunderstanding with my husband.")	Ma'am Golf
		"Nag request na nga ako ng sabado at lingo na off para lang maka uwi sa bahay namin sa pampanga para makasama ko mga anak ko" ("I request Saturdays and Sundays off to go home to Pampanga because my husband and children are there.")	Ma'am Lima
		"kahit tayo pulis at ito ang career natin dapat I prioritize parin natin ang mga anak natin" ("Even if we're police officers and have our careers, we should prioritize our children.")	Ma'am Alpha

Theme 3: Work-Life Balance Issues: Time Strain

Sub-theme: Balancing work and family responsibilities

The text highlights the challenges of balancing work and family responsibilities, especially for a female police officer who is also a mother. The officer talks about how she had to choose between her work and her children and how her job has caused misunderstandings with her husband.

Ma'am Juliet: *"Mahirap maging nanay at maging pulis sa totoo lang kasikailangan mo minsan mamili eh, trabaho o pamilya"*. ("It's hard being a mother and a police officer because you have to choose between your work and your children.")

“Noong nagging patroller ako di kuna masyadong na priotize ang asawa ko at mga anak. Nasa barracks na lang ako kasi mas madali yun pag deployment” (“When I became a patroller, I no longer prioritized my married life because I was always deployed alert, and staying in barracks, which caused some misunderstanding with my husband.”)

These statements by female police officers highlight the challenges of balancing their demanding jobs as law enforcers and their responsibilities as mothers and wives. The first statement emphasizes the difficulty of choosing between work and family. Police officers often work long and irregular hours, and the nature of their job may require them to be away from their families for extended periods. This can strain the relationship between a mother, her children, and her partner (Jackson & Carlson, 1992). Moreover, constantly balancing work and family demands can make them experience a full range of emotions (Morgan, 2018). When such imbalance continues, it may cause acute emotional exhaustion at work and family activities, making them want to withdraw to one role (Farradina & Halim, 2015).

The second statement highlights a demanding job’s impact on a personal relationship. Being a police officer often requires being alert and ready for deployment at any given time, leaving little time for personal matters such as marriage. This can result in misunderstandings and conflicts within the relationship (Wright & Thomas, 2019). Other statements also highlighted a mother’s efforts to prioritize her family, despite the demands of their job, which can only show that some police officers can still prioritize their families. It is essential to balance work and family to ensure that both aspects of life are given adequate attention and care (Heilman & Chen, 2005).

Overall, these statements illustrate the difficulties that female police officers face in balancing their work and family responsibilities. It highlights the need for support from the workplace and the community to create a conducive environment for mothers in law enforcement.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the findings underscore the myriad challenges faced by female police officers in the Philippines, particularly concerning work-family conflict, gender inequality, and navigating a male-dominated field. The data illuminates the influence of cultural context, deeply ingrained family values, and societal expectations, highlighting the significant impact on married female officers. The strong emphasis on traditional family roles within Filipino culture, coupled with the collectivist family structure, introduces distinct challenges, shaping the experiences of these officers as they strive to balance demanding law enforcement careers with familial responsibilities. Addressing these multifaceted challenges necessitates a comprehensive and culturally sensitive approach. Beyond the overarching goal of changing societal norms and attitudes, specific attention must be given to tailoring support systems to the unique cultural context of the Philippines. This includes the imperative implementation of policies that recognize and accommodate the distinctive challenges faced by married female officers, such as addressing work-family balance issues and managing societal expectations placed upon them and their families. Furthermore, in combating gender inequality within the workplace, a concerted effort is required to challenge and dismantle deeply ingrained stereotypes and biases. While Western countries may have made more progress in this regard, the Philippines may need targeted initiatives to accelerate advancements in gender equality within the law enforcement sector.

Creating supportive work environments involves fostering an organizational culture that not only values diversity but also provides resources for managing the unique challenges faced by female officers and their families. This may encompass the development of comprehensive mentorship programs, the establishment of peer support networks, and the initiation of projects that specifically address the emotional and mental strains associated with handling traumatic situations. In addition to these measures, a crucial aspect of comprehensive support involves extending assistance to the spouses and children of female police officers. Implementing family-oriented programs, such as family support initiatives, community engagement programs, childcare assistance, and educational support for children, can significantly contribute to alleviating the burdens on the families of these officers. Moreover, career development and advancement opportunities should be structured to accommodate the specific needs of married female officers. This involves not only addressing gender disparities in promotional pathways but also providing training programs that are attuned to the cultural nuances shaping their experiences in the law enforcement profession. In essence, addressing the multifaceted challenges faced requires a nuanced and culturally informed strategy. By acknowledging and understanding the specific contexts that set them apart from their counterparts in Western countries, we can develop initiatives that resonate with the experiences of these officers and their families. This multifaceted approach aims to create a more inclusive and equitable society that not only recognizes the contributions of female police officers but actively supports the success and well-being of both officers and their families in the complex and demanding profession of law enforcement.

To the Philippine National Police particularly the Department of Psychiatry, to implement a mentorship program for married female police officers as it is essential to address the challenges, they face in balancing their personal and professional lives. In collaboration with the Department of Psychiatry, this program will provide them with guidance, support, and valuable insights from experienced colleagues who have successfully achieved work-life balance. Mentorship, in conjunction with the expertise of the Department of Psychiatry, plays a pivotal role in professional development and personal growth. By pairing married female officers with mentors who have overcome similar challenges, the mentorship program, with the involvement of the Department of Psychiatry, creates a supportive environment for sharing knowledge and wisdom. Mentors, including professionals from the Department of Psychiatry, can offer

practical advice, share strategies for managing time and priorities, and provide insights based on their experiences, which will greatly benefit the mentees. Through this program, in collaboration with the Department of Psychiatry, married female police officers will have the opportunity to gain valuable insights into successfully managing their professional responsibilities alongside their roles as spouses and caregivers. Mentors, including experts from the Department of Psychiatry, can help them identify effective strategies for time management, prioritization, and self-care, ensuring they can fulfill their duties at home and on the job without compromising their well-being. Moreover, the mentorship program, supported by the expertise of the Department of Psychiatry, fosters a sense of camaraderie and solidarity among female police officers. It creates a safe space for open dialogue, allowing mentees to freely discuss their challenges, seek guidance, and receive support from their mentors, including professionals from the Department of Psychiatry. This sense of community and psychiatric expertise are crucial in promoting mutual understanding, empathy, and empowerment within the organization. Additionally, the mentorship program, with the support of the Department of Psychiatry, can significantly contribute to the retention and advancement of married female officers within the PNP. By providing them with the necessary tools and support, the program, in collaboration with the Department of Psychiatry, enhances their professional growth and satisfaction, ultimately increasing their commitment to the organization. Mentees may gain new skills, expand their professional networks, and develop the confidence needed to overcome obstacles and seize opportunities for career progression. To ensure the effectiveness of the mentorship program, in collaboration with the Department of Psychiatry, the PNP must establish clear guidelines and expectations for both mentors and mentees. These guidelines, including specific considerations from the Department of Psychiatry, should outline their respective roles, responsibilities, and the duration of the mentoring relationships. Regular check-ins and evaluations, with input from the Department of Psychiatry, should be conducted to assess the progress and effectiveness of the program, allowing for necessary adjustments and improvements to be made. In conclusion, establishing a mentorship program, in collaboration with the Department of Psychiatry, for married female police officers within the PNP is a significant recommendation. It provides a platform for knowledge sharing, support, and guidance, empowering married female officers to navigate the complexities of their personal and professional lives successfully. By fostering a culture of mentorship and support and incorporating the expertise of the Department of Psychiatry, the PNP can enhance the well-being, retention, and advancement of this marginalized group within the organization.

For future researchers, it is recommended to conduct further studies on the experiences and challenges faced by female police officers and the factors that contribute to their success and advancement in the field. Additionally, exploring the impact of gender diversity and inclusivity in law enforcement agencies can provide valuable insights for promoting equity and creating more effective police departments. Finally, examining the effectiveness of diversity training and programs in police academies and agencies can help identify best practices for creating a more inclusive and diverse law enforcement workforce.

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